

LEarning and action alliances for **NexuS** **E**nvironments
in an uncertain future

LENSES

WP2

D2.2. Activity of the Learning and Action Alliances – Final report

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Activity of the LENSES Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs)

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Executive summary

This report is intended to describe the activities carried out within the “Learning Action Alliances” at the three scales in which they operate (pilot, project and trans-project) **by month 36, the end of the LENSES project.**

As an introduction, it presents the concept of **Learning and Action Alliances**, in general and within the framework of the LENSES project and how they have been articulated at their different scales and levels.

The methodology as a structured approach with three levels, to design and monitor the **implementation roadmap** and the planning of participatory activities undertaken by the seven pilots is also described.

For the **LENSES pilot-LAAs**, the document also summarises the **conducted activities and the lessons learned**. The document highlights key reflections from the pilot's experience during LENSES and the strategies developed by the LAAs in order to face and many times overcome the challenges during the ongoing stakeholder engagement process. The interaction between technical WPs and participatory activities are described in time as well. Finally, each implementation roadmap finalises with the critical review of the pilot initial objectives and what has been achieved by the end of LENSES. The synergies, future initiatives, as well as the so-called “intangible results” steering from the LAAs are highlighted, which are part of the LENSES legacy.

To ease the review process, all seven pilot roadmaps have been compiled into a single Miro board, accessible at <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVKlctFpo=/>. Since the roadmaps encompass a wealth of information, both written and visual, it is preferable to directly access them via the Miro platform. This allows for seamless navigation, enabling users to zoom in and out between sections and across different pilots. The board is publicly available, but only in viewer mode, ensuring privacy and control over the content.

The report also presents the activities carried out during the **project LAA meetings**, the subjects that were discussed, and how these activities created a space for dialogue, trust and exchanges between pilot leaders as well as between pilots and work packages.

Finally, this report includes the **trans-project LAA meeting** between REXUS and LENSES projects, providing a description of these actions as part of the cross-fertilisation achievement.

1. Introduction: “Learning and Action Alliances” and their benefits for Nexus management

Boosting the **integrated management of the water-energy-food-environment (WEFE) nexus** has long been recognized as a critical challenge that requires the cooperation and coordination of stakeholders at multiple levels. However, this challenge has been compounded by the impact of the climate change crisis, which has led to more complex, uncertain and interconnected trade-offs and conflicts. The lack of **communication, coordination, and dialogue between WEFE nexus-related stakeholders** has been identified as one of the main barriers to effective management of the nexus. This has led to today's deep-rooted problems, such as institutional fragmentation, silo thinking and acting, and recognises the need for more transversal approaches to nexus management.

In response to these challenges, **the LENSES project** aims to **place stakeholders at the centre** of the Nexus approach to explore, understand, and tackle trade-offs, related conflicts, management challenges with the goal of co-creating alternative solutions. The adoption of participatory approaches for the co-creation of knowledge can bridge the gap between academic research and the expertise of non-academic actors operating in practice across water-ecosystems-food (WEF) systems, as well as facilitate the dialogue among science and policy realms. This approach also recognizes that stakeholders' interests, expectations and actions are the key elements for change. In fact, changing the behaviour of both individuals and groups of stakeholders, is the channel through which resilient nexus management may occur.

One of the key ways in which LENSES operationalizes stakeholder involvement is through **Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs)**. These discussion-and-action groups are composed of a broad selection of stakeholders who convene through a structured series of workshops, participatory activities, and discussion meetings with the aim of creating communities in which learning resulting from project activities and outputs is directly translated into real action by the affected actors. The LAAs are a dynamic learning process and a living collective body that is expected to evolve by trust building among partners and common achievements.

LENSES' focus on **“social learning”** is a central element in facilitating nexus thinking and driving resilient nexus doing. Social learning is a process supporting a broad range of organisations that frame and reframe the issues at stake in one or several domains and develop enhanced capabilities to deal with common problems which individuals or one single organisation often cannot resolve on their own. Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs) allow for the operationalisation of social learning by building long-term relationships between participants based on **co-producing knowledge**, cooperating in the convergence of ideas, and exchanging knowledge within and between LAAs. The LAAs are made up of actors from various backgrounds, fields, and expertise with the common goal of contributing to the identification and development of solutions and facilitating their local adoption.

The LENSES LAAs also build on the idea of **“learning by doing”** and co-development rather than transfer of knowledge through joint learning where there are no established experts. The ultimate objective it pursues is to achieve **mutual ownership which could increase adaptive capacity and governance**, and facilitate the identification and adoption of innovative solutions for complex socio-technical problems.

The LAAs are organised at three levels in the LENSES project, the pilot level, the intra-project level, and the trans-project level:

- a. **At the pilot level**, co-development, knowledge sharing, and dialogue will be strengthened through a series of visioning exercises for the development of LENSES strategic roadmaps. The pilot LAAs are also the environment within which the System Dynamics Models and visioning approaches are developed, and Ecosystem-based Adaptation is planned.
- b. **An intra-project LAA** will promote mutual learning across the pilot LAAs and address transversal themes, work in progress, and transferability.
- c. **Finally, a trans-project LAA** initiative will facilitate exchanges with other sister projects funded under the same topic, as well as in related calls in PRIMA and other programs.

In synthesis, the use of LAAs in LENSES is expected to facilitate the development of a shared understanding of the complex WEFE nexus issues among stakeholders, enhance their capacity to deal with these issues and ultimately contribute to the development of more resilient and sustainable solutions. By placing stakeholders at the centre of the approach, LENSES aims to overcome the challenges of communication, coordination and dialogue between WEF nexus related stakeholders, and promote a truly interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approach to WEF nexus management.

2. Methods: Implementation Roadmap of Participatory Activities

The LENSES project is a collaborative effort aimed at developing innovative and sustainable strategies in seven different pilot areas across the Mediterranean. Because the project relies heavily on stakeholder participation, which is seen as essential to ensure that the proposed strategies meet the needs and expectations of local communities and other key actors, in order to facilitate stakeholder engagement, the LENSES project has developed a methodology for the implementation of participatory activities in each pilot area.

The methodology was developed over the course of the first year of the project (see **D2.1. “Stakeholder engagement guidelines”**), through a series of participatory activities that involved pilot leaders, as well as work packages 2 and 8. The objective was to create a framework for the allocation of participatory workshops, engagement and dissemination activities in each pilot area. A generic allocation was initially proposed and discussed with pilot leaders ([Figure 1](#)), which was then adapted to the specific aim of each pilot depending on the different focus given to the development of system dynamic modelling, application of visioning or integration of ecosystem-based approaches into the recommended packages of solutions, development of business models for NBS, and so on. The participatory activities were then broken down into workshops involving the participation of the broad group of stakeholders, as well as other side activities where smaller groups of actors could convene to deal with specific topics more closely related to their expertise.

The next step was for each pilot to have customised their own pilot **implementation roadmap of participatory activities**. In order to support the pilot teams in the implementation of the participatory activities, WP2 and WP8 leaders prepared generic boards in Miro software ([Figure 2](#)), which were presented and validated through individual follow-up sessions with each pilot team. These templates allowed for pilot

team members to collaboratively allocate participatory activities in a logical framework, accounting for the type of activity and the phase of the project (*preparatory phase, problem framing, assessment of nexus solutions, validation and action planning, capacity building and knowledge exchange*), the goals of such activity, the needed inputs, expected outcomes, and relation to other activities along a timeline.

The application of the methodology involved three steps. The first step was to choose the participatory activities that were going to take place in the pilots. This involved mapping out engagements in the form of workshops, interviews, focus groups, or any other activity where stakeholders were involved. The second step was to place each participatory activity along the timeline, along with any other activities that were being developed by the scientific team. This allowed for a clear visualisation of the workflow and expected outcomes by the end of the process. The third and final step was to build a pilot narrative that would enable pilot leaders to pitch their activities in LENSES dissemination activities in a simple, direct, and engaging way to stakeholders. In line with LENSES grant agreement (“The Activity of LENSES LAAs will be reported in D2.2 using a blog format”), in addition to the pilot roadmaps, a written section using a blog format has been included, and it is expected to be published in various platforms, such as the LENSES website and learning platform.

The results of this exercise are described in the next section, broken down by pilot area, with a specific focus on participatory activities. Overall, the methodology developed by the LENSES project is expected to contribute significantly to nexus actions by involving stakeholders at every step of the process. This approach is expected to help build a sense of ownership and responsibility for the proposed strategies, which is critical to their long-term success.

5 “Regional Meetings” (tentative timeline and content)

Figure 1. LAA Methodology. Tentative timeline and content for the five pilots' Regional Meetings

Implementation Roadmap

Learning and action alliances for Nexus EnvironmentS in an uncertain future

The purpose of this step is to map what participatory activities are going to take place in the pilots (clearly, implemented and ongoing). These engagements can be in the form of a workshop, interviews, focus groups, etc. By participatory activity we mean any activity where stakeholders are involved (collecting needs, discussing problems, discussing options), with their inputs in the back (meeting, or other analytical work) should be described in the following step. To facilitate the overview we have provided as example a preliminary list of participatory activities that all you are planning to fully or largely implement. Please feel free to add/delete/modify those only those that you intend to apply to the best of your current knowledge.

Map each participatory activity along the timeline. In addition to participatory activities, you can use any other activities that are developed by the scientific team, if they help you to visualize the logic of the workflow. You can use connection lines, arrows, stars, circles, notes, shapes, dates, and so on.

Figure 2. Initial template provided for the creation of the pilot implementation roadmap

3. Progress of the Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs)

3.1 Pilot LAAs

3.1.1 Deir Alla (Jordan)

The pilot is testing the use of unconventional water resources, such as wastewater and saline water, as an innovative solution to address food production challenges related to the Nexus. The scarcity of freshwater resources, the high demand for water in agriculture, and the negative impacts of climate change are some of the main challenges that the pilot aims to tackle.

The main objective of conducting this study is to evaluate the cultivation of Alfalfa crop, which consumes high amounts of irrigation water. This will be in comparison with the use of crop rotations of both summer and winter crops in terms of water saving, economic and environmental aspects. The aim is to propose a new formulation for animal feed, demonstrate the value of intercropping and what would be the right management of it to be an effective alternative to alfalfa crops, using less water and producing good quality animal feed.

Field activities

The pilot activities conducted in the Jordan Valley involved observing vegetable crops from December until the late of May and early June, and summer field crops such as corn and okra from April to the end of August. Date palms were observed throughout the year with the production season from August to October, while citrus could be seen all year round, with the production season from October to December. The pilot also involved silage making, where all plots were harvested and chopped using a drive shaft chopper before being mixed separately and compressed using a hydraulic compressor in plastic barrels for silage making. Molasses was added during the compressing process as a source of fermentable carbohydrate for bacteria. After 45 days, samples were collected from each treatment and analysed using both proximate analysis and NIR technology. Proximate analysis included moisture, ash, crude protein, neutral detergent fibre, acid detergent fibre, and ether extract. Data was collected to measure biomass produced for each forage plot to evaluate economic value. Different proportions of intercropped silage were made in plastic barrels to ensile the mixed crop. Finally, preparation was made for winter crops, with barley replacing sesbania and vetch replacing sorghum to ensure crop rotation for the 2022/2023 winter season. The main findings from the experiments indicated that silage quality would be evaluated at NARC Lab, and results would be available soon. Additionally, water and soil analyses were conducted, with mixed water from King Talal Dam being used for irrigation, and soil nutritional analysis showing good fertility levels but moderate salinity. Sorghum productivity under pilot conditions was 125-ton green forage per hectare, while Sesbania productivity was 48-ton of green forage per hectare.

Participatory activities

Several stakeholder activities have been conducted in each season. During the first winter season (2022), a **technical workshop** was held in order to demonstrate the **reduction costs of feed** to cattle hoarders. While conducting analysis from the first silage production and after planting the second season of Barley and Vetch, there were **demonstrations of silage management practices**. The pilot team members presented alternatives to, especially, alfalfa crops which use **less water** and produce good quality silage.

In the first summer season (2023), the NARC team has also **organised visits** during the growth period, as means to disseminate the pilot activities. During this season another participatory activity was organised as means to showcase the **methods of silage production** to local goat and sheep breeders. In mid-march 2023, the NARC team planned a **field trip** for the LENSES team as part of the joint Jordan-Israel plenary meeting. Ongoing visits were used to disseminate the activities to farmers as well. Some stakeholders were highly interested in the quality of feed for dairy cattle. They tried the feed during the silage-making season, collecting and applying it themselves

During the second winter season (2024), while the team performed sorghum and systania lab analysis of nutritional value (assessments have been conducted always at the beginning and at the end of each season, accounting for water savings as well as soil quality); two workshops are scheduled and are expected to be conducted by end of **May 2024**, when the second summer season begins, as means to provide stakeholders with a full picture of LENSES pilot results (the NARC team needs to analyse the winter results). The expected silage data results from both winter and summer crops will be a direct input to this workshop, as well as a cost-benefit analysis which aims to demonstrate the value of intercropping and what would be the right management of this practice. It is expected that participants will include **farmers and the Water Society of Jordan Valley**, among other relevant stakeholders. The second workshop will be targeted especially for farmers, with a practical format. The attendees will primarily consist of members from the Women's Cooperative, as well as other cooperatives from the North East region, including Irbid and Mafraq (around 30 participants). It will consist of a **technical "training" workshop** to demonstrate the nutritional value of various silage varieties; with some farmers attending already using NARC technology.

In conclusion, the key message of the Deir Alla pilot area is that **integrating crop rotation with animal feeding can be mutually beneficial**, resulting in reduced water consumption and nutritious, locally produced and environmentally friendly products.. The NARC team aims to persuade farmers to adopt crop rotation practices, especially considering the precise irrigation requirements they face. Despite the existing water limitations, **with only 70-75% of the true irrigation needs** being met for winter crops up to May. This situation **is becoming increasingly challenging to sustain summer crops** in the Jordan Valley.

Most farmers operate on a small scale, and unless they have access to an additional water source, traditional farming practices may no longer be viable. Thus, transitioning to more water-efficient management practices like crop rotation becomes essential for sustainable agriculture in the region. The challenge lies in **convincing and enabling farmers** to adopt the approach promoted by NARC. Even when the quality of the silage produced is superior to that of alfalfa silage, and while the alternative requires less water and offers improved nutritional value, along with enhanced soil quality due to increased nitrogen levels, **alfalfa still holds appeal for farmers**. Its longevity, lasting up to seven years, and its multi-cut capabilities make it a preferred monocrop for many.

NARC technology offers an alternative through intercropping, aiming to strike a balance between water conservation, nutritional quality, and soil health. By emphasising these benefits, the team hopes to encourage farmers to **reconsider their current practices** and explore more sustainable and efficient farming methods. This has been partially achieved already, as part of the LENSES project legacy: **some farmers are already using the technology** offered by NARC and are becoming more and more directly involved, being considered as **strategic partners** (directly benefiting and being a target group). Also, the outputs from the project are to be compiled as a **policy brief** for policy makers from the Jordan Valley Authority.

Figure 3. Deir Alla implementation roadmap. Available at: <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVKlctFpo=>

3.1.2 Hula Valley (Israel)

The Hula Valley pilot aims to assess the potential of **agro-photovoltaic (APV) technology and nature-based solutions** to address Nexus challenges. The challenges in this pilot are related to the limited availability of water resources and the need to increase the efficiency of water use in agriculture while maintaining ecosystem services, as well as governance issues. Regulations do not favour APV technologies as they are perceived as a potential risk to competing land uses, and expected to cause trade-offs between the agricultural and energy sectors.

The pilot aims to address this challenge by helping farmers to diversify their livelihoods. The simulation of installing plastic sheets about the trees instead of the panels gave the team a good estimation on the effects when APV will be installed, but this has to be approved. If the regulation barriers the pilot is experiencing were solved, this approach allows for activities such as food and energy production to be compatible, while ensuring ecological benefits, such as saving water in orchards and enhancing biodiversity. The stakeholder engagement efforts aim to overcome such barriers, foster dialogue among stakeholders, and promote the adoption of Agro-Photovoltaics and other sustainable farming methods for a resilient agricultural future.

The **main achievement** of the Hula Valley Pilot was in **proving the water saving potential by implementing APV in orchards, with minimal negative impact on the fruit production**. The results achieved are good and the farmers were satisfied with the possibilities to implement APV in their orchards. The LENSES APV approach fully implemented at the Kineret Watershed **will free about 15% irrigation water** in orchard fields, to nature, achieving solutions to a basin-level WEFE nexus challenge.

Following there is a description of the **many meetings** the pilot team had with farmers, regulators, industrialists and managers at the Kibbutzim regarding the LENSES project and the results of the experiments done:

- **Pilot experimentation:** the APV methodology testing was done with two different APV companies in two different orchards, in Kibbutz in the valley and in another Kibbutz on the mountain.
- **Pilot dissemination:** Multiple meetings have taken place between the Netafim irrigation factory and the orchard manager at Yiftah to discuss the idea of implementing APV. Additionally, there have been several meetings held with the Economic CEO and delegates from Agri-Light panel's industries at Kibbutz Yiftah, as well as with officials from the Upper Galilee Regional Council to discuss the potential application of the proposed system to Galilee orchards.
- **Regulation barriers:** there are ongoing discussions with the office at the Department of physical planning at the Regional Authority.
- **Ongoing Bilateral Meetings with domestic and international Energy Companies:** MIGAL has ongoing discussions with various energy companies, including DORAL, to explore potential collaborations in Israel and beyond. This company has an APV Experiment in Israel with MIGAL: as part of the experiment, MIGAL has been actively involved, and promising cases are beginning to emerge, which could serve as bottom-up examples for wider adoption. They are also in contact with Arilight and many other energy companies to lead the APV initiative and drive its implementation.
- **SunnySide 2024 APV Conference (Israel + International) 2-4/04/2024.** The conference adopted a bottom-up approach to explore the nexus between conflicts and synergies in agriculture. Results

from the PSDM were instrumental in defining roundtables, each focusing on a different topic. The conference attracted over 400 participants.

- The last day of the conference featured a **workshop 04/04/2024** with a large number of participants from Israel, primarily virtual attendees. The workshop, titled *"Implementing agrivoltaics in peripheral regions as an economic engine"* was **led by MIGAL in partnership with USAID**, and had a panel with experts (n =11) in diverse knowledge realms. This workshop focused on implementing Agro-Photovoltaics (APV) in the field. It attracted over 50 participants, predominantly from Middle Eastern countries. **The ultimate aim is to support the revival of the innovation-based APV industry in the Middle East and expedite its commercial utilisation:**
 - a. Initiated an objective dialogue among competing agents in Israel, including the **Ministries of Agriculture, Foreign Affairs, Energy, and Environmental Protection Directorate** Key Outcomes of this workshop were (i) the validation of barriers preventing AVP scale-up, laying the groundwork for addressing challenges with the necessary parties; and (ii) the start for farmers to explore new agricultural practices, indicating a shift in mindset towards more sustainable methods. The workshop placed a significant emphasis on the development and promotion of effective policy making and knowledge transfer, focusing on encouraging the implementation of APV system technology in perennial crops.
 - b. Successfully addressed the needs of **six key stakeholder groups: scientists, farmers, policymakers, producers (including VP, IT, and energy sectors), investors, and local action groups**. The first step for a long-term strategy for multi-stakeholder collaboration on APV implementation and promotion in Middle Eastern countries was therefore established.

In conclusion, the pilot's initial goals have been achieved despite its especially challenging circumstances. Even with restrictions to test the innovative APV technologies, the team assessed the potentials for saving water and protecting fields from extreme climate events (droughts, frosts, etc.), with minimum impact to fruit production. Given the social, economic and political barriers to APV, the pilot started an objective dialogue between the competing agents, which are the Agriculture, Energy and Environment ministers of Israel with the idea to validate the barriers previously identified by this research, and explore how intersectorial challenges are affecting the governance of the nexus. Furthermore, the MIGAL colleagues have also been able to partner with other early adopters of APV in neighboring countries.

Along with these practical outputs and their future potential, the Hula Valley pilot raised a concern regarding **the prioritisation of certain topics in WEF nexus research. Energy is integral to the Nexus**. Current trends in the Nexus research focus on agriculture and carbon sequestration while underlooking the energy dimension. In that respect, the MIGAL team is actively seeking new funding opportunities in the UAE, Jordan, and Morocco to take their initiatives one step further. Ultimately, the goal this pilot area strives for is to demonstrate that it is possible to diversify farmers' livelihoods, by producing food and electricity, while ensuring ecological benefits, such as saving water in orchards and causing positive impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem services.

Figure 4. Hula Valley implementation roadmap. Available at: <https://miro.com/app/board/uXiVKlctFpo/>

3.1.3 Koiliaris

The Koiliaris Critical Zone pilot in LENSES integrates field experiments aimed at reducing water demands in avocado crops with the assessment of nature-based solutions (NBS) on water scenarios. The challenges in this pilot are related to the high water demand of agriculture and the need to reduce the pressure on water resources in the region. Additionally, policy-related issues impact farmers' behaviour and do not favour the uptake of agricultural practices aligned with the vision of NBS.

The pilot has a long history of engagement with the local avocado farmers association, around 17 years of collaboration. The focus with this group of stakeholders has been to develop a causal-loop diagram (CLD) which focuses on WEF impacts related to irrigation technology. At this stage, the CLD has reached a high level of detail in problem framing.

The first participatory activity consisted of two focus groups (25/10/2022). During the **first focused group** farmers from the avocado farmers' cooperative (n= 12) were discussing a vision of water resources availability in the area, the effectiveness of the current irrigation practices and potential strategies to overcome existing barriers to innovation on irrigation. The second group performed a **visioning exercise** with avocado farmers from the Koiliaris area (not part of any association, n =6). Due to its past history, the fragmentation of land into small parcels, the fact that most farmers had other jobs in addition to taking care of their farms, and low prices in agricultural products have led to decreases in agricultural productivity and profit. Today, the need for cooperation between farmers is seen as necessary to achieve sustainable economies of scale. The CLD was also reviewed. The results were shared with WP4 to finalise the CLD, and WP3 provided policy scenarios.

Parallel to these discussions, the Koiliaris team members were performing **soil analysis and irrigation monitoring**, accounting for soil structure, organic carbon, fertility, and biodiversity parameters.

The next participatory activity consisted in a **training workshop (26/07/2023)** for the avocado farmers association, in which the results from the field experiments on WEF nexus optimisation were presented and discussed with them. The pilot presented data regarding the inputs from WP3, WP4, and the analysis of physical and biological samples to prove farmers with the benefits of adopting more ecologically sound practices. Although the participant sample size was high and well balanced (n = 40, averaged between 30-75 years old) the engagement was perceived as low, as only about 13 farmers engaged in the discussion.

Other participatory activities focused on cross-fertilisation was the **Jordan Valley project meeting** which took place in early October 2023, and the final meeting at a conference in Crete focused on "Story as a driver of change."

The **last Koiliaris workshop** took place on **April 4th 2024**, with the aim of presenting and validating the final LENSES results for the pilot area. With a participant sample size. N = 39 (37 legislators from the Region of Crete, 2 participants from the Technical University of Crete), the Koiliaris pilot leader Nikolaos Nikolaidis gave a presentation titled *"Workshop for the transfer of good practices for the optimization of WEF Nexus – Introducing tools for optimising WEF and NBS"*. The presentation focused on the tools created within the framework of the PRIMA LENSES project (NBS Selection tool, stakeholder participation tools, NBS assessment tools), and the pilot demonstration for the optimization of the WEF nexus. The presentation concluded with the following three questions for discussion: (i) did you find the tools presented useful? (NBS Selection Tool,

Participatory Modelling Tools (CLD, PSDM, ABM) and is it possible that can be used by policy makers?; (ii) Which one will be most likely to be adapted?; and (iii) how can we communicate the pilot results for maximum impact?. According to the pilot leaders, the last workshop was a success, and stakeholders are demanding more events like it in the future.

In conclusion, the Koiliaris pilot has achieved its primary goal in terms of stakeholder engagement, which was **to utilise LENSES results as a convincing tool for implementing WEFE solutions in the face of climate challenges** in the area. The results derived from the LENSES project can serve as a compelling tool to advocate for the implementation of Water-Ecosystems-Food-Energy (WEFE) solutions in response to climate challenges. By demonstrating the efficacy and potential impact of Nature-Based Solutions and sustainable practices identified through LENSES, stakeholders can be encouraged to prioritise and invest in WEFE solutions as part of their climate resilience strategies.

Overall, the aim of the pilot is to determine the benefits of optimising the WEF nexus by decreasing irrigation, increasing organic carbon, and improving soil structure and agricultural production. However, the team is not yet at the co-design stage, and potential farmer misadaptations are part of the problem. For the pilot, it is critical to understand what policy context would improve the uptake of NBS. There is an underlying issue affecting farmers related to the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and the subsidies received. In that respect, the main difficulties the team faces relate to making an impact on farmers and policy makers' choices by showcasing the project results.

Moving forward, **there is a need for more genuine and active listening that pushes stakeholders into taking real action**, particularly farmers and managers, to better understand each other's needs, concerns, and priorities. Convincing them to establish together a new physical network, consisting of massive training initiatives, deployment of field sensors, and development of new indicators, will be crucial for enhancing the resilience and sustainability of agricultural practices in the region.

Last but not least, the Koiliaris team members strive to foster a **paradigm shift** in the ways of doing and relationships between farmers, researchers, and regional managers. Creating opportunities for co-creation, knowledge exchange, and mutual learning can facilitate the development of shared goals, trust, and effective communication among stakeholders. Emphasising the value of interdisciplinary collaboration and recognizing the diverse perspectives and contributions of all stakeholders can help build a more cohesive and resilient network capable of addressing complex challenges and driving positive change in the Koiliaris region.

Preparatory phase

Problem framing

Assessment of Nexus solutions

Validation and action planning

Capacity building, and knowledge exchange

Figure 5. Koiliaris implementation roadmap. Available at: <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjvKlctFpo=/>

3.1.4 Pinios

The Pinios pilot has conducted several participatory activities which the team members reported as of **high effort and very satisfactory**. This is because there is an excellent connection to local stakeholders. The LENSES tasks implemented include among others, the hydrological model, the NbS efficiency simulation and writing of publications. The SWAT model is implemented in Agia watershed (PHO) to quantify the hydrological processes, as well as the effects of agricultural practices. Irrigation and other practices are incorporated in the model after information from local farmers. SWAT and SEAWAT models have been updated in Pinios River Delta to quantify the hydrological processes and the effects of agricultural practices. These tasks and their integration with the engagement process are reflected on the LAA roadmap ([Figures 6, 7, and 8](#)).

The **participatory activities** that have taken place already are:

- **Stakeholders mapping (09/2021) and interviews (12/21-1/2022)**. Following D2.1 guidelines, the pilot determined stakeholders' hierarchy levels to be covered, drawing up a list of appropriate stakeholders. Then, they ensured a diversity and well-balanced stakeholders' representation of all nexus sectors and drew up an extensive list of crucial WEF challenges to be addressed. 19 Stakeholders were interviewed. For each challenge, the focus was on determining crucial areas, current state, barriers, indicators and climate change impacts, as well as the identification of interrelations between nexus challenges.
- **First young farmers' seminar (18/05/2022)**. The goal was to allow future young farmers to familiarise with modern agricultural technologies of Pinios Hydrological Observatory.
- **Field trip (05-06/09/2022)**. During the field trip, partners were able to visit the pilot areas and gain insight into their characteristics and main challenges. This visit helped to initiate closer collaboration among the partners. In addition, key terms related to nexus management were presented, and networking with the sister REXUS project was conducted to promote the significance of the LENSES project.
- **ABC/J Students' trip (24-25/09/2022)**. Aimed to educate foreign future young farmers from different cultures about modern technologies used in the Pinios Hydrologic Observatory (PHO) and spread the word about the holistic approach.
- **Lenses Window start up (10-11/2022)**. At the start of the Lenses Window, the main modules were defined. This includes a presentation and description of the pilot areas, research team, main challenges, main targets, and news about the LENSES project.
- **First workshop (21/11/2022)**. In the first workshop, the following actions were taken: the final determination, confirmation, and prioritisation of challenges, problems, obstacles, strengths, opportunities, and indicators; the co-identification of cross-sectoral dependencies; the analysis of indicators; the development of sectoral qualitative models, which involved creating Causal Loop Diagrams (CLD); and the visioning of a Business as Usual (BAU) future.

- **Second young farmers' seminar (30/03/2023).** The second young farmers' seminar presented the nexus system of the Pinios pilot area, including their main challenges and interrelations. The seminar also aimed to increase the awareness of young farmers on the nexus approach.
- **Second workshop (05/05/2023).** Focused on developing what-if scenarios, the first part of the visioning exercise, and the use of NBS. During this workshop, the integrated CLD was presented, and the drivers and hidden interrelations between challenges explored. The stakeholders explored drivers and hidden interrelations between the challenges and defined specific targets for each defined goal/ challenge. Policy regulations were incorporated and discussed as previously analysed by the SRWI team in order to focus on the most appropriate for the workshop. Finally, NbS scenarios for the sub-basins were defined as opportunities for nexus sustainable development.
- The **second (12/05/2023) and third (26/05/2023) young farmers' seminars were** held at the Athens-Siggrou Agricultural Vocational School and the Crete-Messara Agricultural Vocational School, respectively, both of the Hellenic Agricultural Organisation. The venue for the upcoming seminar will be the Averoff Agricultural Vocational School of Larissa. The purpose of these seminars was to present the Pinios pilot areas nexus systems, highlighting their main challenges and interrelations, with the aim of increasing young farmers' awareness of the Nexus approach. During the sessions, there were presentations on the project's philosophy and the WEF (Water-Energy-Food) Nexus approach. Additionally, the developed irrigation services were introduced as a tool within the Water-Energy-Food-Environment Nexus system, particularly focusing on their relevance under conditions of climate change.
- A **Cafe meeting (14/12/2023)** was intended to plan NbS assets and implementation, refine scenarios based on preliminary model results, co-finalize NbS, and co-determine assessment criteria for measures.
- **Third workshop (21/02/2024).** The third workshop focused on co-creating solutions and a business plan. It will involve a review of challenge indicators based on stakeholder perceptions, presentation of sustainable NbS solutions, presentation of present and future conditions produced by models, and defining NbS's value delivery. The goal was to co-decide and verify with stakeholders the proposed measures and the usability of the tools developed throughout the LENSES project. Also, a participatory Political Economy Analysis activity was performed, analysing the actors involved and power dynamics available to accelerate sustainability visions (see D2.4).
- **Open day/ results' presentation event (21-22/02/2024).** The Open Day/ Results Presentation event laid the foundation for the post-LENSES period by promoting a broad consensus among stakeholders in the pilot areas regarding the outcomes of LENSES. The highlights of the project were showcased, and the evaluation of the progress and outcomes. Lastly, the project results were rendered available for future projects in the pilot area.

In conclusion, the main results achieved and some unexpected “spillover effects” from the LENSES Pinios pilot can be summarised as follows:

- **Educational Impact and Awareness:** Introduction of the Pinios Hydrologic Observatory at Agricultural Schools engaged students and prospective young farmers, enhancing their understanding of hydrology and agriculture's interplay. Training of young farmers on complex nexus

systems under the LENSES project improved their competencies in modern agricultural technologies and environmental stewardship.

- **Stakeholder Engagement and Network Strengthening:** Effective dissemination of the LENSES project news and results fostered informed local stakeholders and the general public. Strengthened ties and collaboration among stakeholders through various activities, including the co-development of strategies and the co-finalization of Nature-based Solutions (NbS). Nevertheless, more efforts to **widen the stakeholders' pool and to mobilise the active participation of farmers** are needed. One of the key challenges the pilot is facing regarding stakeholder engagement is that **some stakeholders - farmers specifically - often view "scientists" as disconnected from their reality** and not particularly useful. These efforts aim to demonstrate to stakeholders, particularly small farmers, that LENSES is not just another research project and that what "scientists do" is relevant and not disconnected from their "real" lives. The pilot team members are working to promote the holistic approach of LENSES, especially to younger generations of farmers. The LENSES project's learning platform, LENSES window¹, is a crucial tool for engaging and educating farmers in NBS and relevant nexus sound practices. The platform aims to connect farmers with similar farmers from other Mediterranean regions. However, it is important to note that the language used in the LENSES project and in science in general can be difficult to communicate to farmers using an online platform that uses technical jargon.
- **Strategic Development and Validation:** Identification and validation of challenges and results, ensuring that the solutions proposed are reflective of stakeholder viewpoints and real-world applicability. Development and formulation of scenarios tailored to address specific environmental and agricultural challenges in the region.
- **Implementation and Sustainability of Solutions:** Pilot areas strategy co-development and NbS bundles selection focused on leveraging local insights for effective solution implementation. Ensured sustainability of solutions post-Lenses project, maintaining environmental benefits and community involvement.
- **Comprehensive Analysis and Methodological Advancements:** Present and future situation analysis provided a detailed understanding of the basin's stresses, enhancing the project's relevance and targeted approach. Evaluation of the usefulness of tools and methodologies developed, ensuring their effectiveness and adaptability for continued use.

Unexpected Results:

- **Wider Reach and Influence:** The project results unexpectedly spread beyond local stakeholders, reaching a broader "world" of Thessaly and potentially influencing other regions and sectors, indicating the project's extensive impact and relevance.
- **Enhanced Stakeholder Involvement:** Perhaps unforeseen was the level of stakeholder engagement and the diversity of involvement, which may have led to a more enriched dialogue and comprehensive understanding of local needs and possibilities.

¹ <http://www.lenseswindow.eu/login/index.php>

- **Technological Adoption and Interest:** Increased interest and quicker adoption of modern agricultural technologies than anticipated, showing a significant shift in local farming practices towards more sustainable methods.
- **Evaluation Insights:** The evaluation of tools might have revealed new uses or modifications that could be applied in other contexts, suggesting that project outcomes have broader applications and potential than initially expected.

Figure 6. Pinios implementation roadmap (map of activities). Available at: <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVKlctFpo=>

Figure 7. Pinios implementation roadmap (graphical representation). Available at: <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVKlctFpo=/>

Figure 8. Pinios Implementation roadmap. Available at: <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVKlctFpo/>

3.1.5 Menemen plain in Gediz basin (Turkey)

The Menemen plain is located within the Gediz basin in Turkey. This pilot project aims to develop an **ecosystem-based basin management approach** to ensure sustainable agriculture and food supply. The Nexus challenges in this pilot are related to efficiently managing water resources to meet the growing demand for agriculture and protect the ecosystem services provided by the Gediz basin. The demonstration and dissemination of nature-based solutions as well as the development of a green vision for the basin are the solutions provided by LENSES to this challenge.

Fieldwork activities involving sampling of groundwater and soil have been conducted, as well as workshops and training activities:

The **first stakeholder meeting (08/12/2021)** was an introduction to the project for both policy makers and a small number of farmers (focused primarily on policy makers). The main objective was to identify the main problems affecting the basin from the WEF perspective, as well as developing the relations in terms of organisational issues between stakeholders. A questionnaire was conducted to identify current challenges and stakeholder arrangements. Suggestions regarding SDG and NbS were discussed as well.

The first of a **series of dissemination activities on NBS** began on **January 27th 2022**, in synergy with LENSES WP9 activity, a “training on efficient irrigation” session was held at UTAEM to raise awareness of farmers regarding the sustainable management of water resources. This session was informed as well as served as input for the teams’ earth observation analysis of water accounting, allocation and planning for the pilot, in parallel with the fieldwork for groundwater and soil observations (March-June and May-September 2022, respectively). The samples from 279 points in the pilot area were characterised by pollution.

The **second stakeholder meeting (04/11/2022)** focused on farmers. The main activity was a participatory visioning development as well as the depiction of the pilot in the shape of a Causal Loop Diagram (CLD). Both the farmer version and policy maker version of the CLD were implemented, both versions compared. Another survey was conducted using a questionnaire to determine farmer behaviour as responses to the challenges in the region (how they were collectively and individually coping) for 30 farmers. The team made an introduction of NbS as a multidimensional term, followed by a discussion on possible NbS for the area and a Q&A. Dissemination of the Nexus concept, especially linked to NbS, was also introduced to participants by the UTAEM team.

Due to the drought in the region, **theoretical and practical training sessions** were organised in Menemen for producers to learn about the efficient use of water in agricultural production. Demonstrative activities were planned in the farmers' fields in three themes: 1) *increasing microbial fertilisers* to reduce the use of chemicals; 2) *intercropping* by planting legumes in orchards to improve soil quality and reduce the use of chemicals; and 3) demonstrating regenerative practices to the farmers. The scheduled activities were executed throughout 2023.

The **third stakeholder meeting (17/01/2024)** accounted for a total of 27 participants, including researchers, farmers as well as relevant stakeholders and policy makers for the pilot area. The main outputs from the fieldwork will be the presented, as well as the experience of NBS activities in the farmers’ fields, to build a green vision for the future of the basin. The next part of the participatory visioning was conducted, in which participants described both business as usual and sustainability scenarios for each nexus dimension. The

scenarios were developed through the prioritisation of measures over time. Participants were asked to select a few critical measures to reach sustainability visions (with a focus on NbS) in order to perform on these a participatory Political Economy Analysis: each measure was analysed in terms of barriers and opportunities on the one hand, as well as on the actors and power to implement them, on the other. More details on the visioning process and the analysis of the measures from power/ actor behaviour perspective can be found in D2.4 "Strategic Roadmaps for Nexus futures"

In conclusion, the Menemen pilot project has successfully facilitated the provision of valuable Nexus-based analysis for integrated soil and water management in agriculture and ecosystems. The team has effectively utilised these findings, along with training sessions and other participatory and dissemination activities, to enhance comprehension of practical solutions addressing the significant challenges currently faced by farmers in the pilot area.

Furthermore, there have been notable outcomes, occasionally intangible but highly pertinent for stakeholder engagement purposes. These include:

1. Synergies across multiple stakeholders in the conservation and reclamation of soil and water resources through a nexus approach.
2. Establishment of a robust collaboration with the Menemen Chamber of Agriculture, with potential future collaborations on NB) to provide farmers with materials such as microbial fertilisers developed by UTAEM, which are essential for agricultural production processes.
3. The adoption of the "NEXUS Approach" has proven instrumental in integrating discussions about the holistic management of Water-Energy-Food-Ecosystems resources, as well as the promotion of the term "Nature-Based Solutions." Though it required time, this approach garnered the attention of both farmers and other stakeholders, thereby fostering systems thinking among farmers. Consequently, farmers are now considering Water-Food-Ecosystems interdependencies in their everyday practices.

Figure 9. Menemen Implementation roadmap. Available at: <https://miro.com/app/board/uXiVKlctFpo=/>

3.1.6 Tarquinia

The main Nexus challenges in the Tarquinia plain are related to both the quantity and quality of water in agricultural areas. Also, there is a lack of collaboration sharing data between researchers and local authorities. There are well intended basin management strategies in place but they have not been fully implemented, as a result of institutional fragmentation.

Continuous contact has been made with stakeholders at various levels and timescales. As field experiments were not possible, data was collected from various databases. Most of the engagement was done in person or through conversations. The pilot faced the challenge of using official channels and online tools, which were slow and not suitable for effective engagement. Nevertheless, the pilot builds upon the previous FATIMA project in the area², which allowed for conducting a baseline analysis of key resources, actors and pressures aimed to engage stakeholder involvement in the project. More stakeholders were included using a snowball process, which led to **interviews** and the organisation of a **mini workshop** online during the confinement period **(01/12/2021)**. The workshop focused on the development PSDM method; additional PSDM interviews were conducted. *At its initial stage, **mutual learning activities**, tapping into actors' deep understanding of specific local dynamics, served to better frame the complexity of the Nexus and build a common understanding of local societal challenges as well as of potential innovations in farming practices, land, and water management.*

The **second workshop (26/05/2022)** consisted on the participatory mapping for the identification of nexus challenges, CLD validation and the first step of the visioning process (*problem framing*). This process has allowed the pilot team to develop the CLD for the study area and conduct analysis such as Social Network Analyses in order to gain understanding of the interrelations between key agents and resources underpinning nexus security.

The **third regional meeting** took place on **29/04/2023** with the objective of presenting and discussing the results of LENSES. The meeting allowed us to gain insight from stakeholder contributions and their points of view regarding the research, especially the results on PSDM-CLDs, Climate change projections and Risk indicators. This way, the WP4 team gained feedback on the analysis that will support scenarios and implement the stock and flow model. The visioning exercises for the regional meeting were prepared between WP2 and WP3 and potential policy interventions were discussed in plenary to overcome the main barriers in the Tarquinia area and develop possible policy scenarios.

Finally, the last and **fourth workshop** took place on 16/04/2024, and consisted in two meetings: one directed to key stakeholders (policy makers and high ranking technical profiles from the municipality) and another to students and teachers of secondary schools. The first part focused on presenting the PSDM and scenarios results, as well as the land use assessment and the selected NbS for the pilot area. These were afterwards discussed in plenary followed by a Q&A. The second part focused on the dissemination of the LENSES approach and the results for Tarquinia in a simpler manner. Climate change projections were also presented and discussed. Finally, the LENSES serious game was tested with students and teachers to gain feedback on its usefulness to foster complex thinking with respect to nexus management.

² <http://fatima-h2020.eu/pilots/italy-piana-di-tarquinia-lazio/>

In conclusion, the Tarquinia pilot has provided data and results which serve as an evidence-based “solution selection framework” to decision makers and other stakeholders, to support the selection of measures to address nexus challenges in a holistic way. This process has allowed the pilot team to enhance stakeholder engagement in the area.

By following the LAA approach, the Tarquinia colleagues have served as orchestrators of a dynamic change in the way stakeholders interact with each other. The approach has allowed for transitioning from merely requesting data to the establishment of a network characterised by collaborative, non-hierarchical “co-creation” with plans to expand this network to national level in the future. The team has successfully gained the commitment from farmers, the municipality of Tarquinia and the ecoregion to utilise LENSES results for comparison with their current agendas, and are already involved in future project proposals: (i) the establishment of a living lab in Tarquinia, enabling farmers to directly contribute to research through field studies on Nature-based Solutions (NbS) and agroecological practices, and (ii) enhancing city wastewater systems to increase drought resilience during the hot season in partnership with the municipality.

Figure 10. Tarquinia Implementation roadmap. Available at: <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjvKlctFpo=>

3.1.7 Doñana

The Doñana pilot is focused on **developing a strategic roadmap** to improve the management of the Water-Ecosystems-Food nexus, which is crucial due to the increased pressure of water resources overexploitation and climate change on regional resilience. The roadmap integrates visioning and PSDM methodologies as core elements, combining participatory methods with expert-based research. The roadmap elaboration will integrate other LENSES tools such as policy analysis, NBS bundles, and water accounting.

During the **first year** of the project, the study area was delineated and the baseline description of the pilot was elaborated. Two bundles of NBS have been identified, and a time series of irrigated crops maps covering the full study area was produced. During November 2021, ECOADAPTA and IRSA conducted **semi-structured interviews** with key stakeholders to collect information on main sectoral challenges, key pressures, and existing impacts, among other things. The information was used to elaborate the socio-ecological network analysis and the Causal Loop Diagram (CLD), which are core inputs for the System Dynamics Model (SDM). Finally, the pilot implementation roadmap ([Figure 11](#)) allowed team members to map the participatory activities along with the LENSES methodologies to be applied in Doñana for the rest of the duration of the project.

The **first workshop** in the Doñana pilot took place in **October 2022**, organized by ECOADAPTA in collaboration with IRSA and Agrisat. Its focus was on validating the CLDs and discussing potential solutions to the main systemic challenges. The activity was based on the application of the participatory mapping methodology developed within WP2 and WP4, using maps and a set of cards depicting main resources, socio-economic activities, pressures, impacts and potential interventions. The items included in these cards come from the information gathered through the interviews. The focus of the workshop was to validate the CLDs, as well as deepen into the discussion on the elucidation of key Nexus challenges, i.e., moving from sectoral challenges into systemic challenges. Furthermore, the participants started the discussion on potential solutions to the main systemic challenges and provided meaningful information for the initial design of desired scenarios through a specific exercise using the Mentimeter tool. There was also time to introduce the progress of LENSES as well as the next steps in the participatory roadmap for the pilot to all the attendants.

During 2023 the **Task 3.2**, "Mapping and analysing political and policy context with policy makers", led by ECOADAPTA, was developed and tested during previous months and served as an input for the workshop and roadmap. This **political-economic analysis (PEA)** will integrate the results from WP2, WP3 and WP4, especially to understand the "business as usual" behaviours of stakeholders and tap into the right incentives to transition towards a more resilient, conflict-free Doñana region. This is expected to increase the saliency and operational implementation of the visioning exercises and roadmaps resulting from the workshops. The **PEA** methodology was tested in Doñana using **interviews** (between December 2023 and February 2024) (n = 9 farmers and n = 5 WEFE stakeholders), a **workshop** and **two focus groups**, to analyse the points of view from stakeholders. Although the focus groups had the same purpose (investigate farmers' behaviour, especially with respect to innovative irrigation practices), the two groups of stakeholders were significantly different in terms of power.

The **second workshop (12/12/2024)** used a semi-quantitative participatory approach to develop visions, pathways and narratives, using the CLD interrelation, and the most up-to-date, relevant policies for the area, and the inputs from the PEA interviews. The measures of the visions were analysed using the PEA

participatory methodology with great success, and afterwards have been replicated in the Pinios and Menemen pilot areas (more details on D2.4).

The **first focus group (13/12/2023)** was organised in el Rocío with **9 farmers from the farmers' irrigation community "Puerta de Doñana"**, which have consolidated their exploitations throughout the past decades, acquiring legal water rights and managing them collectively, and have significant leverage on policies being applied in the area, as the economic value of their products for export is very high and their farms can be considered as labs for high-tech irrigation. Their pain point is to have enough voice to conduct restoration efforts with the right support of the political realm. This first focus group was organised in collaboration between ECOADAPTA, IRSA, AGRISAT and UNIDP.

The **second focus group (15/12/2023)** targeted the most vulnerable farmers—both women and men—working in the fields of Huelva. These individuals arrive in the province and struggle to find decent housing while simultaneously engaging in illegal farm labour under extremely harsh conditions. Additionally to the development of the ABM, the goal of this activity was to enlarge the pool of stakeholders, especially accounting for those who have been underrepresented in earlier stages of the project, therefore addressing the lack of engagement with less powerful stakeholders. A **total of 9 immigrants** participated, along with 3 volunteers (a lawyer specialised in racism, a Spanish language teacher, and the president of the non-profit association ASNUCI), and the ECOADAPTA team. Several script adaptations were necessary due to their differences in education levels and fluency in Spanish language, which may result in limitations in the outcomes that therefore need to be interpreted cautiously.

Several participatory activities will be conducted after the end of LENSES. For instance, the conclusions of these two focus groups are currently being translated into an academic paper.

The **upcoming third workshop is expected to occur in June 3rd 2024** and will focus on the **validation of the PSDM-ABM** with a selected group of expert stakeholders. Afterwards, there will be **dissemination** activities concerning the model, the PEA and the roadmap; including presentations the LENSES approach and results in general. The ECOADAPTA team is especially focused on the potential usefulness and transferability of LENSES to the **Ministry of Ecological Transition of Spain**, which is responsible for the implementation of the restoration and socioeconomic development plans for the area, as they currently like a model for the analysis of different measures, which the PSDM-ABM allows for. Also, we see the model as a valuable tool for dissemination of the Nexus among stakeholders, which includes managers, end-users, but also importantly, the youth (student community) and the society at large.

In conclusion, the Doñana pilot objectives have been achieved, as the primary goal from the team members was to **produce "actionable knowledge"** to be part of the solution to the increasingly degrading status of the ecological hotspot that Doñana represents. The integration of a PSDM-ABM model will enable the validation of the feasibility of the roadmap, while the PEA will render the assumptions regarding stakeholders' roles and responsibilities in implementing the action more realistic and tactical. This, in turn, may make the desired futures achievable, leading to the realisation of the "strategic roadmap towards a resilient nexus system in the Doñana region." This actionable knowledge aims at improving water management by co-designing solutions that integrate both inbound and outbound water bodies, thereby expanding towards a nexus system that transcends the boundaries of the national park, including all relevant parties in the pilot area, independently of their power status.

the LENSES project DOÑANA PILOT

Learning and action alliances for Nexus EnvironmentS in an uncertain future

1) NEE bundle for increasing hydrology connection between Guadalupe river and Doñana marshlands
Assessment of NEE bundle
Ecosystem services valuation methods
Restore wetlands to areas of groundwater recharge
Recover rivers with floodplain to enhance natural water storage
Rivers or canals, including connectivity, respecting Blue corridors
Floodplain restoration and management

2) NEE bundle for optimization in the use of resources for agriculture and increase of biodiversity
Erosion of continuity of ecological networks (prevention from fragmentation)
Agroecological practices
Soil improvement and conservation measures
Increase of water holding capacity and infiltration rates
Agroecological network structure
Wildlife
Incorporating maresca, carrizales, or incorporating crop residues to enhance carbon storage

Irrigated crops (2020)
Doñana Protected Area
Barren
High density with 200 Guadalupe
Irrigated herbaceous crops
High cover woody crops (e.g. olive)
Low cover woody crops (e.g. olive)

Learning and action alliances for Nexus EnvironmentS in an uncertain future, LENSES, Project pilot Areas, Doñana (Spain)

ASSESSING THE SUSTAINABILITY OF AGRICULTURE AND ECOSYSTEM SERVICES IN THE DOÑANA REGION

The pilot area includes the Doñana marshlands, one of the most valuable wetlands in the Mediterranean region, being the second site for more than 100,000 water birds each year. However, the region is the largest bird producer and one of the most important for wildlife and even humans. Climate change and human use of resources are seriously compromising the sustainability of inland agriculture and the conservation of the environmental heritage of Doñana, forest and forest systems, and agricultural are required to ensure resilience of the whole agro-ecological system.

GENERAL DESCRIPTION:

- The pilot area encompasses the Doñana National and Natural Parks as well as the cultivated areas during water resources (E, surface and groundwater) with the Doñana marshlands.
- Location: South-west of the Iberian peninsula, within the Mediterranean region.
- Main economic activities: Agriculture and stockbreeding.
- Area: 10,000 ha.
- Doñana is an UNESCO World Heritage site because of its exceptional value for the conservation of biological diversity.
- More than 600 ha of forests, 21,000 ha of oak and 1,000 ha of marshes are included in the pilot area.
- The National Emergency Plan is currently activated.

LENSES GOALS

- Contribute to improve water resources management by creating a resilient area to face various future conditions.
- Sustainable high-value agricultural activity in a context of water scarcity (increased by climate change).
- Better adaptation to more frequent and intense droughts.
- Conserving ecological reserves for recreation, regulation, cultural, from Doñana marsh areas currently closed by subsidence of marshes and water channels.
- Improved water allocation between competing activities.
- Implementation of innovative digital farming.

Figure 11. Doñana Implementation roadmap. Available at: <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjvK1ctFpo/>

3.2. Project LAAs

The regular project LAA meetings have been a cornerstone of the overall LAA approach. These meetings aimed to **facilitate knowledge exchange between LENSES pilots and technical work packages** with a focus on mutual learning and cross-fertilization. This involved exchanging experiences regarding Nexus challenges, comparing innovative solutions to current sectoral approaches, and identifying barriers and drivers for the adoption of systemic solutions. This work has been essential to highlight key transferability issues for the successful uptake of the solutions in a different context.

The project provides a **space for discussion around transversal topics** addressed by LENSES pilots, and has been facilitated by ECOADAPTA as leader of WP2. The LAA meetings have been mostly held virtually, with occasional in-person meetings coinciding with larger project meetings. The LAA meetings have been organised on a monthly basis throughout all the project.

In conclusion, the project-LAA meetings played a critical role in the LENSES project. With **recurring meetings** scheduled for the first Monday of every month from 10:00 to 11:00 CET, the project have provided a platform for pilot-to-pilot meetings, WPs to pilot meetings, thematic sessions with key stakeholders, and even trans-LAA sessions. Additionally, as a group, it was possible to collectively set the project-LAAs agenda and identify topics for discussion that are important to the LENSES project. All LENSES pilot areas worked together to make these meetings productive and valuable for all participants.

The **first project LAA (03/12/2021)** focused, as a first step, on the main aspects regarding the functioning of this LAA (i.e., what is the project LAA, who will participate in the meetings, what are the potential topics to be addressed, and how often, when and for how long will the project LAA convene) were presented, discussed and agreed between the pilot leaders. As a second step, ECOADAPTA produced a presentation on tips and key aspects to be considered and addressed for the organisation of a successful workshop.

The **second project LAA (07/03/2022)** provided an initial presentation of the learning platform, which ignited a discussion with the pilot leaders about objectives and potential functionalities to be added into the online tool.

During the next **project-LAA (06/06/2022)**, ECOADAPTA presented the generic structure for the realisation of a roadmap of participatory activities, where technical workshops and other dissemination workshops involving the broad group of stakeholders are assimilated to the Regional Meetings. Finally, the initial version of the guidelines for stakeholder engagement were presented, and questions related to the suggested approach for stakeholder mapping were answered back.

The **fourth project LAA (09/01/2023)** focused on a recap of the stakeholder engagement process so far ([Figure 12](#)). SWRI presented the other pilots the design and results from the first technical workshop in the Pinios pilot, including the presentation of lessons learnt and tips to improve the organisation. ECOADAPTA prepared the following set of questions for pilots to reflect and engage in debate:

- *How would you describe the engagement until now: very satisfactory, good, difficult/can be improved?*
- *What are the greatest difficulties you have/are encountering in LAA building?*
- *What has worked well in your LAA building approach so far?*

- *What hasn't worked so good? Any ideas on what needs to be done to overcome existing barriers?*
- *Give a concrete example of how LENSES scientific approaches will be used by stakeholders*
- *Give a concrete example from your pilot area of how the LENSES approach (the project outcomes) will help address a basin-level WEF E Nexus challenge and change outcomes?*

Figure 12. Example of an online LAA Meeting (09/01/2023)

The **fifth project-LAA** took place on **January 30th 2023** and focused on the D2.4 “Report on LENSES strategic roadmaps for Nexus Future”. ECOADAPTA presented the core elements of the deliverable, including the practical steps for organising workshops 2 and 3 of the visioning process. ECOADAPTA also prepared Miro boards for pilots to answer questions regarding their interest in the visioning process, and to what extent they intend to apply it (Figure 13). This is meant to facilitate giving future support to pilots.

Deir Alla

Question 1. Are you planning to implement the visioning exercise or part of it?

Question 2. Would you be interested in combining the qualitative visioning exercise with PSDM? Or would you only stay with CLDs? or none?

Question 3. Would you be interested in combining the qualitative visioning exercise with NBS frameworks for the development of the pathways?

Question 4. When do you foresee to have the next workshop? How much time you think you could allocate for this activity?

Gediz

Question 1. Are you planning to implement the visioning exercise or part of it?

Question 2. Would you be interested in combining the qualitative visioning exercise with PSDM? Or would you only stay with CLDs? or none?

Question 3. Would you be interested in combining the qualitative visioning exercise with NBS frameworks for the development of the pathways?

Question 4. When do you foresee to have the next workshop? How much time you think you could allocate for this activity?

Galilee

Question 1. Are you planning to implement the visioning exercise or part of it?

Question 2. Would you be interested in combining the qualitative visioning exercise with PSDM? Or would you only stay with CLDs? or none?

Question 3. Would you be interested in combining the qualitative visioning exercise with NBS frameworks for the development of the pathways?

Question 4. When do you foresee to have the next workshop? How much time you think you could allocate for this activity?

Tarquinia

Question 1. Are you planning to implement the visioning exercise or part of it?

Question 2. Would you be interested in combining the qualitative visioning exercise with PSDM? Or would you only stay with CLDs? or none?

Question 3. Would you be interested in combining the qualitative visioning exercise with NBS frameworks for the development of the pathways?

Question 4. When do you foresee to have the next workshop? How much time you think you could allocate for this activity?

Pinios

Question 1. Are you planning to implement the visioning exercise or part of it?

Question 2. Would you be interested in combining the qualitative visioning exercise with PSDM? Or would you only stay with CLDs? or none?

Question 3. Would you be interested in combining the qualitative visioning exercise with NBS frameworks for the development of the pathways?

Question 4. When do you foresee to have the next workshop? How much time you think you could allocate for this activity?

Koiliaris

Question 1. Are you planning to implement the visioning exercise or part of it?

Question 2. Would you be interested in combining the qualitative visioning exercise with PSDM? Or would you only stay with CLDs? or none?

Question 3. Would you be interested in combining the qualitative visioning exercise with NBS frameworks for the development of the pathways?

Question 4. When do you foresee to have the next workshop? How much time you think you could allocate for this activity?

Doñana

Question 1. Are you planning to implement the visioning exercise or part of it?

Question 2. Would you be interested in combining the qualitative visioning exercise with PSDM? Or would you only stay with CLDs? or none?

Question 3. Would you be interested in combining the qualitative visioning exercise with NBS frameworks for the development of the pathways?

Question 4. When do you foresee to have the next workshop? How much time you think you could allocate for this activity?

Figure 13. Planning for visioning participatory activities in LENSES pilots

During the **sixth project-LAA**, which took place on **February 28th 2023**, the UNIDP colleagues provided an overview of the ecosystem services indicators and their development, with examples of implementation, describing the work done in **Task 6.1 “Socio-economic valuation on NBS: assessing ES”**. The session started with a short presentation of the methodology and the work done in Koiliaris pilot, making the aims of the indicators and the logic behind their development clear, as well as providing an overview of the indicators themselves and examples in terms of implementation. The focus of the remaining time was on clarifications and discussion, particularly on the identification of data availability at the pilot scale, which was identified as a bottleneck for the exercise. A Miro board was used to map the pilots’ needs and goals ([Figure 14](#)). The second part of the meeting further clarified questions regarding mapping ecosystem services indicators and possible datasets that can be used for biophysical and economic quantification.

Downscaling to your pilot areas: which data are available?

Figure 14. Planning for ES assessment in LENSES pilots

On **March 27th 2023**, the LAA meeting focused on the learning platform LENSES window and its usability since its launch in June 2022. Since then, pilots were asked to log in the platform and designate a responsible person for updating its contents. The main questions discussed were about the platform's ability to enhance institutional and governance capacity, its usefulness in encouraging discussions between stakeholders, and its role in establishing a governance mode for implementation and monitoring of roadmaps. The conclusion was that some pilots find the platform relevant, while others doubt its engagement potential. It was also noted that some pilots are using the LENSES website and observatory, as well as their own social media channels, instead of the platform, which highlights the importance of collaboration between WP2 and WP9 regarding dissemination of pilot activities and producing contents.

The **7th project-LAA (27/03/2023)** focused on a Q&A on **Lenses Window** and Q&A on synergies between LAAs and **Dissemination** (WP9 - "Pathways to Impact"). Pilot leaders updated on the ongoing or recent activities, as well as planned ones.

The **8th project-LAA (30/04/2023)** focused on the **validation** of LENSES methodologies by stakeholders. This meeting was organised in close collaboration with WP8 "Pilot Implementation" which fosters the implementation and validation of the LENSES solutions and innovations in the six pilot countries and supports local communities and institutions in the paradigm shift towards operationalising a Resilient Nexus. Their methodology was presented and there was a Q&A between the pilots and WPs.

The **9th project-LAA (29/05/2023)** focused on a Q&A on **cross-fertilisation**, as means to gather information from pilots which were collaborating directly or indirectly with other nexus projects. A jamboard was used for the purpose.

The **10th project-LAA (25/09/2023)** meeting was a **cross-fertilisation project meeting** with the colleagues from another Nexus project, **the H2020 REXUS project**. A mentimeter exercise was conducted in order to match topics, challenges, and technical solutions being developed by LENSES and REXUS pilots, which account for a total of 12 pilot areas working on the integration of the Nexus using PSDM.

The **11th project-LAA (30/10/2023)** was focused on organising internally how to prepare for the upcoming REXUS-LENSES plenary meeting, in which each pilot area was bringing a stakeholder. The meeting focused on a brainstorming session in order to ease the process of designing the sessions that were going to be given by the LENSES team, as well as the joint activities with REXUS colleagues, and the ideas of participatory activities for attending stakeholders.

The **12th project-LAA (27/11/2023)** focused on an online training on **Political Economy Analysis workshop activities**, led by ECOADAPTA. The team presented the materials that had been designed and that were going to be tested in the second Doñana workshop, answering questions from pilot leaders which wanted to replicate the methodology during their upcoming workshops.

The **13th project-LAA (29/01/2024)** focused on the presentation of the results from Doñana 2nd Stakeholder workshop, followed by a Q&A.

The **14th project-LAA (8/03/2023)** focused on presenting the final integration of all these activities into the "**D2.4: Participatory Strategic Roadmaps**", followed by a Q&A.

The last and 15th project-LAA (30/04/2024) focused on evaluation and feedback. Pilot leaders reflected about the usefulness of the LAA approach, with a focus on determining the positive contributions as well as any significant shortcoming of the process.

A first round of questions assessed whether the LAA have been or not a useful tool to support the development of the project. Answers are summarised in [Figure 15](#).

Figure 15. Feedback of the pilots to the LAA approach (1)

A second round of questions addressed the utility for the pilots of the regular LAA project meetings. Answers are shown in [Figure 16](#).

Figure 16. Feedback of the pilots to the LAA approach (2)

Finally, we include below some of the conclusions and remarks from the pilot leaders in relation to the LENSES LAA process:

- The systematic approach to stakeholder engagement through the LAAs has been invaluable to guide pilots through the process and to ensure that a maximum impact is achieved.
- Stakeholder engagement is of utmost importance in problem understanding and even more in paving ways to sustainability. Making a stakeholder feel as an active actor of a project definitely strengthens its willingness to seriously participate in the project implementation.
- The LAAs have provided an important support to mutual learning through the sharing of ideas, encouragement, boosting and guidance.
- The collaboration and communication between the technical partners, the pilot leaders and the coordinators of the LAA meetings/workshops have been key to the success of the project implementation.
- LAA meetings have helped pilot leaders to fully understand what to exactly expect from their stakeholders so they could design the participatory exercises accordingly. It was emphasised that a large part of the results obtained have been strongly supported by the participatory component provided by the LAAs.

3.3. Trans-project LAAs

The **e-webinar** that took place on **January 18th, 2023** was the first **Nexus e-dialogues**, which aimed to share information and learnings about best practices in place across Mediterranean countries and beyond, to proactively address the complex risks driven by climate change. The experiences of Jordan and Israel pilots were presented, followed by lessons learned from the "Diverfarming project" in Italy and agroforestry and intercropping experiences in Spain. There was a Q&A session and closing remarks.

**1ST LENSES E-DIALOGUE WEBINAR:
ADOPTION OF WATER-ECOSYSTEMS-FOOD-ENERGY
NEXUS IN AGRIFOOD SYSTEMS ACROSS THE
MEDITERRANEAN BASIN**

18 January 2023
Online h 10:30 CET

Open to everyone upon registration: REGISTER HERE

Objective: share information and learnings on best practices in place across Mediterranean countries and beyond, to foster the adoption of water-ecosystem-food-energy nexus approach to proactively address the shifting and complex risks driven by climate change

10:30	Welcome of participants Tiziana Pirelli, Council for Agricultural Research and Economics - CREA	
10:35	Experiences from LENSES pilots - Stefano Fabiani, CREA <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jordan - New forage crops for fodder production in a changing climate Luna Al-Hadidi, National Agricultural Research Center – NARC • Israel - Photovoltaic for sustainable orchard irrigation Uri Marchaim, Galilee Research Institute - MIGAL 	
11:20	Lessons learned from "Diverfarming" project - Roberta Farina, CREA <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Italy - Crop rotation experiences Silvia Vanino, Claudia Di Bene, CREA • Spain - Agroforestry and other intercropping experiences Virginia Sánchez-Navarro, Technical University of Cartagena - UPCT 	
11:40	Q&A session - Moderator: Tiziana Pirelli, CREA	
11:55	Closing remarks - Anna Osann, Agrisat Iberia	

Organizzazione e coordinamento: T. Pirelli; S. Vanino; R. Farina; A. Di Fonzo; F. Pucci; S. Fabiani
Comitato tecnico: E. Gerardi; F. Ambrosini

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Figure 17. Agenda of the first LENSES e-dialogue webinar

Another webinar was organised by the CREA team in close collaboration with pilot leaders. The **2nd LENSES PRIMA webinar "New Technologies and AI tools VS Natural Based Solutions: Trade off and Synergies for Sustainable Agriculture" (4/04/2024)** which focused on sharing knowledge and lessons learned from the NBS and Water Management Pilot areas, Koiliaris (NBS) and Gediz (water management) targeting various stakeholders from decision makers to farmers and academic researchers. More information on these activities and other synergies between LAAs and dissemination can be found in the [LENSES website](#).

Finally, the trans-LAA meeting which had the most impact, was the **REXUS - LENSES Joint 5th Plenary Meeting**, hold in Larissa, Greece, **between Tuesday 7th November 2023 – Thursday 9th November 2023**. From the technical point of view, presentations were prepared individually for both REXUS and LENSES projects, but some were done jointly as several partners were part of both consortiums. Each pilot area (7 from LENSES, 5 from REXUS) brought an important stakeholder to participate in the plenary. From the pilot point of view, pilots were presenting their progress in a joint format with their stakeholder counterparts. In addition, two stakeholder sessions were organised, which were focused (i) Nexus Thinking and (ii) Nexus Doing. The first half focused two key questions: Sectoral or trans-sectorial management, how are we doing? Green vs grey solutions: can they coexist?; and the second session focused on establishing a common

baseline (where are we & how are we going forward?) and creating a roadmap. An artist was present and created simultaneously the visual storyline of the discussion (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Visual storytelling: “from Nexus thinking to Nexus doing”

4. Conclusions and way forward

This report provides an overview of the activities carried out within the Learning Action Alliances (LAAs) at different scales in the LENSES project, up to Month 24. The report begins by introducing the concept of LAAs and how they are structured within the LENSES project, along with the methodology used to design and monitor the implementation roadmap and plan participatory activities for the seven pilots.

For the LENSES pilot-LAAs, the report summarises the activities conducted and lessons learned, including reflections on the challenges faced during stakeholder engagement and the strategies developed by the LAAs to overcome them.

The report also highlights the activities carried out during project LAA meetings, which provided a space for dialogue, trust, and exchange between pilot leaders, as well as between pilots and work packages. Overall, the report demonstrates the effectiveness of the LAA approach in fostering collaboration and co-development of systemic solutions, and provides valuable insights for future projects seeking to implement similar approaches.

The LENSES LAAs have proven to be an effective approach for organising participatory activities in the three scales in which they operate. Stakeholders in all pilots are actively participating in fostering participatory activities, as means to foster co-design, and co-development of systemic Nexus solutions. Additionally, the LAA approach has been crucial in identifying synergies between WP2 and other WPs. For example, WP2 and WP4 actively collaborated to combine participatory mapping with the development of system dynamics models, and a similar collaboration was organised during one project-LAA for selecting NbS by the pilots. Also, regular and active interaction and exchange between pilots occurred.

Although WP2 coordinated the LAA activities, there was a strong support by WP8 - 'Pilot implementation' through regular weekly meetings and joint elaboration of implementation roadmaps, as well as with WP7 on 'Pathways to impact' through joint activities aimed at amplifying implementation and dissemination of LENSES pilots.

The final feedback from pilot leaders on the LAA approach has been highly positive, stressing the fact that the structured approach to stakeholder engagement derived from the LAAs has facilitated a sustained engagement. On top of that, pilot leaders highlighted that the LAA approach has been a learning exercise itself for them, which has delved into new ideas and supported an enhancement and refinement of the planned work, leading to a more successful implementation.

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